

**SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL TO “INTRASEASONAL TEMPERATURE VARIABILITY IN A SHELF-INCISED
VALLEY IN THE SOUTHWESTERN TROPICAL ATLANTIC”**

**S2 – EEMD DECOMPOSITION OF THE FORCING TIME SERIES USED IN THE TEMPERATURE-VARIABILITY
ANALYSIS**

This supplementary section presents the EEMD decomposition of the forcing series retained for comparison with temperature variability at 82 m inside the Zieta shelf valley. Figure S2 shows the original forcing records together with their main variability modes and residuals, allowing the temporal structure of each forcing to be visualized before the TDIC analysis. The forcings include intermediate-depth absolute current velocity at the GEOMAR mooring, sea surface height above the geoid and sea surface height anomaly, and the remote zonal and meridional wind-stress indices. Table S2 summarizes the main components of these forcings and identifies those selected for comparison with the temperature modes in Section 3.2. Together, Figure S2 and Table S2 provide the decomposition basis used to interpret the statistically significant forcing-temperature relationships discussed in the main text.

Figure S2. Main variability modes obtained from the Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition (EEMD) of the forcing series examined in relation to temperature variability at 82 m inside the Zieta shelf valley. In each panel, the original forcing time series is shown at the top (red line), followed by the main EEMD components and the residual (blue line). (a) Absolute current velocity averaged over the 134–212 m layer at the GEOMAR mooring KPO1170, after application of a 56-hour lag. (b) Sea surface height above the geoid at P1 and the corresponding sea surface height anomaly at 34.83°W, averaged over the 8.83–10°S latitude band; no lag was applied. (c) Mean zonal wind stress over 0–22°S, 2°W–15°E, after application of a 28.5-day lag. (d) Mean meridional wind stress over 22–25°S, 40–42°W, after application of an 8-day lag. The lags correspond to empirical temporal offsets applied before EEMD, based on the simple lagged correlation that maximized the overall correspondence with the original temperature record at 82 m.

Table S2. Main EEMD components of the forcing series investigated in relation to temperature variability at 82 m inside the Zieta shelf valley. For each forcing, the table summarizes the main variability modes, their average periods, explained variance, and maximum amplitudes. The highlighted components are those used in the Time-Dependent Intrinsic Correlation analysis described in Section 3.2, i.e., the forcing modes that showed statistically significant relationships with the temperature variability modes.

KPO1170 - Absolute velocity (134-212m) - lag: 56hours			
	Var (%)	Period (days)	Max. amplitude (m/s)
C7	6.2	1.3	0.08
C8	5.4	2.5	0.08
C9	6.5	6.4	0.06
C10	16.1	15.7	0.09
C11	6.7	22.6	0.06
C12	48.9	74.2	0.11

Sea Surface height above the geoid - P1			
	Var (%)	Period (days)	Max. amplitude (m)
C9	11.9	9.4	0.043
C10	10.1	14.1	0.023
C11	74.4	47.5	0.057
C12	2.8	73.1	0.008

Sea Surface height anomaly at 34.83°W (latitude band: 8.83-10°S)			
	Var (%)	Period (days)	Max. amplitude (m)
C9	8.5	8.1	0.017
C10	16.0	18.4	0.032
C11	74.3	49.0	0.033

Mean Zonal wind stress (0-22°S 2°W-15°E) - lag: 28.5 days			
	Var (%)	Period (days)	Max. amplitude (N/m ²)
C7	6.4	1.1	0.02
C8	24.3	3.1	0.03
C9	32.5	7.7	0.02
C10	18.5	15.9	0.02
C11	10.1	35.6	0.01
C12	5.3	70.6	0.01

Mean Meridional wind stress (22-25°S 40-42°W) - lag: 9 days			
	Var (%)	Period (days)	Max. amplitude (N/m ²)
C7	8.1	1.2	0.08
C8	29.8	3.5	0.10
C9	21.7	6.5	0.07
C10	19.1	13.6	0.05
C11	9.4	35.2	0.04
C12	6.5	48.9	0.03